

Real-Time Human Activity Monitoring for Feedback-Driven XR Training

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Abstract. XR-based training environments enable detailed monitoring of user behavior during complex procedural tasks, creating opportunities for real-time performance assessment and feedback-driven, context-aware guidance. This paper presents a system designed to support XR-enabled procedural training by i) monitoring and analyzing how tasks are executed rather than simply recognizing actions; ii) tracking and comparing trainee motion trajectories with expert demonstrations to assess motion compliance; iii) managing procedural progression across task phases; iv) detecting execution deviations and performance indicators in real-time; and v) computing structured corrective feedback through rule-based evaluation and LLM-assisted reasoning, currently externalized through a supervision interface pending full XR integration. The proposed approach aims to enable interpretable and adaptable feedback during XR training, translating motion deviations into corrective suggestions that support more effective learning of complex procedural tasks. The system is demonstrated in an XR-based aircraft maintenance training scenario involving technicians performing maintenance procedures on a Wing Anti-Ice Valve. Future work will integrate these feedback mechanisms directly within the XR environment and evaluate the approach in realistic training scenarios.

Keywords: Human Activity Monitoring · Extended Reality Training · Performance Feedback · Motion Analysis · Procedural Task Monitoring

1 Introduction

Human activity understanding is a critical research field spanning Computer Vision, wearable sensing, robotics, and immersive Extended Reality (XR) environments. Most of the existing literature focuses on Human Activity Recognition (HAR), defined as the identification of discrete actions from sensor or vision

data using Machine Learning or Deep Learning techniques [1, 2]. HAR systems primarily address the question of *which* action is being performed and are typically evaluated through classification accuracy on annotated datasets. While highly successful for action identification [3], such approaches remain insufficient for applications requiring continuous performance assessment, procedural supervision, and real-time training support.

In many real-world scenarios, understanding human behavior requires more than recognizing individual actions. Training environments, industrial operations, and medical procedures require the ability to monitor *how* activities are performed over time, assess execution quality, and provide guidance during task execution. Consequently, recent research across multiple domains increasingly addresses continuous monitoring, interpretation, and performance assessment of human behavior. The literature has expanded from activity recognition to broader notions of *human activity analysis*, where activities are not only detected but interpreted in terms of structure, intent, and execution dynamics [4–6].

In healthcare and ambient assisted living, *human activity monitoring* approaches focus on continuous observation of behavior over time to assess performance and behavioral evolution rather than discrete action labels [7]. In robotics and Human-Robot Collaboration, research on *activity understanding* and semantic reasoning models activities through contextual and task-aware representations, enabling interpretation and prediction of goals and procedural progress [8, 9]. Similarly, *workflow and process monitoring* studies in domains such as surgical assistance and industrial operations represent activities as sequences of structured phases, allowing verification of procedural correctness and transition consistency [10, 11]. Parallel efforts in *skill and performance assessment*, particularly in surgical training and sports analysis, evaluate the quality of execution by comparing user behavior with expert references, focusing on deviation analysis and performance metrics rather than classification accuracy [12–14].

To reflect this broader perspective, we adopt the term **Human Activity Monitoring and Analysis (HAMA)**, which denotes an integrated view combining execution monitoring with semantic analysis. HAMA emphasizes the transition from action recognition toward comprehensive activity understanding and execution assessment. Instead of assigning activity labels, monitoring systems evaluate deviations from reference executions, procedural progression through task phases, semantic correctness of actions, and achievement of task outcomes. This perspective is particularly relevant in training scenarios involving complex procedural tasks. Operators must not only perform the correct sequence of actions but also execute them with appropriate motion, timing, and coordination. However, traditional training approaches often rely on manuals, videos, or instructor supervision, providing limited opportunities for continuous monitoring and real-time feedback [15, 16].

Immersive XR environments offer new opportunities to address this limitation. By combining spatial tracking, interactive virtual content, and contextual task information, XR systems can capture detailed information about user behavior while preserving realistic task conditions and natural interaction [17].

This sensing capability enables monitoring approaches that relate body motion and interaction patterns to task progression during training. As a result, XR-assisted training environments can evolve from static instructional platforms toward systems capable of continuously observing trainee behavior and providing context-aware feedback during task execution [18].

In this context, procedural training can benefit from monitoring systems that analyze user behavior in real-time and compare trainee executions with expert demonstrations. The work presented in this paper is motivated by an XR-based aircraft maintenance training scenario involving technicians performing maintenance procedures. Within this setting, expert demonstrations and trainee executions can be captured in the same immersive environment, enabling direct comparison between reference and observed behavior during training sessions.

Building on these opportunities, this study investigates how HAMA techniques can support performance assessment and feedback generation within XR-based training environments, by characterizing execution quality and task progression. The main contributions of this work are: i) a conceptual taxonomy for HAMA paradigms, spanning from motion-level analysis to task-aware representations; ii) a work-in-progress monitoring system for XR training capable of tracking motion compliance and procedural progression in real-time; and iii) a feedback generation pipeline combining rule-based evaluation with Large Language Model (LLM)-assisted reasoning to produce interpretable corrections.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews related work on HAMA and training in XR environments. Section 3 presents the proposed solution, including the XR training use case and the implemented approach. Section 4 illustrates the current system, concluding in Section 5.

2 Related Work

Human activity monitoring has been investigated across multiple research domains, including computer vision, robotics, and pervasive sensing. In this work, we focus on approaches that analyze how activities are executed over time in order to assess performance and procedural correctness in XR environments. The literature relevant to this work can be broadly divided into two areas. First, traditional approaches for modeling and evaluating human activity execution. Second, research on training systems based on XR technologies, which provide immersive environments and rich sensing capabilities for observing user behavior during complex procedural tasks.

2.1 Human Activity Monitoring and Analysis Approaches

Human activity understanding has traditionally been addressed through HAR methods, which classify actions from sensor or vision data using Machine Learning techniques [19]. While effective for identifying discrete actions, HAR approaches typically focus on determining *which* action is performed and are evaluated through classification metrics such as accuracy or F1-score [20, 21]. However, many real-world applications require understanding not only *what* action

occurs but also *how* it is executed over time and whether it satisfies procedural objectives. To address these limitations, recent research has expanded toward broader activity analysis perspectives that evaluate execution quality, task progression, and contextual interpretation of human behavior [5, 6]. Several adjacent terms appear in the literature to describe this broader perspective. For example, Human Behavior Analysis (HBA) generally refers to high-level interpretation of human actions, often focusing on behavioral patterns, social interactions, contextual inference, or long-term behavioral trends across different application domains [4]. Similarly, the term Human Activity Analysis (HAA) is often used to denote approaches that go beyond simple action recognition to interpret activity structure and contextual or temporal relationships between actions [22]. In contrast, HAMA is used to describe monitoring-oriented approaches that combine perception and performance evaluation to analyze how actions are executed, how they evolve over time, and whether they conform to procedural objectives. In this work, HAMA is adopted as an organizing framework that unifies these perspectives, complementing rather than replacing existing terminology, and emphasizing the transition from discrete action recognition toward continuous execution assessment in training and operational contexts.

From a methodological perspective, activity monitoring approaches can be broadly categorized according to the representation used to model human behavior. Specifically, they progress from motion-centric methods focusing on kinematic fidelity, to task-structured representations capturing procedural progression, and finally to multi-level approaches that integrate motion and contextual information for more comprehensive activity understanding.

Motion-centric monitoring represents human activities through continuous kinematic signals such as skeletal trajectories or tool motion paths. Temporal alignment techniques such as Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) enable comparison between observed and reference trajectories while compensating for execution speed variations [23]. Motion-based analysis has been widely applied in domains such as surgical skill assessment [12], expertise evaluation through motion smoothness metrics [13], sports biomechanics [14], and collaborative industrial assembly monitoring [8]. These approaches allow precise quantification of execution fidelity but may be sensitive to natural variations in movement style or human characteristics and lack explicit modeling of task structure.

Task-structured monitoring represents activities as sequences of procedural states or milestones. Instead of focusing on trajectory similarity, monitoring evaluates whether task progression follows expected phases and objectives. Several models have been proposed to encode relationships between actions, objects, and task goals, including object–action complexes [24] and probabilistic activity models [25]. Structured representations are also widely used in workflow-driven domains such as surgical phase recognition [10] and industrial process monitoring [11]. These approaches are robust to execution variability and capture task progression, but may overlook detailed motion quality.

Multi-level monitoring integrates motion-level analysis with structured task representations to obtain a more comprehensive view of activity execution.

Such approaches combine continuous sensor streams with contextual or semantic reasoning layers to jointly evaluate motion dynamics and procedural correctness. Examples include context-aware monitoring systems in smart environments [26, 27], sensor-based behavioral monitoring frameworks [28], and hierarchical activity models for complex environments [29]. While these systems provide richer representations of human activity, they typically require integration of heterogeneous sensing modalities and domain-specific task models.

Table 1 presents representative implementations of these approaches across different application domains.

Table 1: Summary of categorized activity monitoring approaches

Ref.	Year	Application Context	Underlying Model
<i>Motion-Centric Monitoring</i>			
[23]	2009	Rehabilitation motion analysis	DTW trajectory alignment
[12]	2019	Surgical training evaluation	Motion feature modeling
[30]	2021	Motion sequence comparison	Spatio-temporal trajectory
[13]	2023	Surgical expertise evaluation	Motion smoothness metrics
[14]	2024	Sports biomechanics	Motor variability analysis
[8]	2024	Collab. assembly monitoring	Multivariate control charts
<i>Task-Structured Monitoring</i>			
[24]	2011	Robotics manipulation modeling	Object–action complexes
[25]	2016	Human activity prediction	Semantic activity reasoning
[7]	2022	Elderly activity monitoring	Behavioral routine modeling
[10]	2022	Surgical workflow analysis	Phase classification models
[31]	2024	Procedural task assistants	HAR-driven task modeling
[11]	2025	Industrial workflow monitoring	Process mining models
<i>Multi-Level Monitoring</i>			
[26]	2020	Smart environment monitoring	Context-aware sensor fusion
[27]	2021	Ambient intelligence monitoring	Multi-sensor behavioral analysis
[32]	2021	Contactless activity sensing	Computational imaging modalities
[28]	2024	Human behavior monitoring	Sensor-based activity analysis
[29]	2024	Multi-layer activity recognition	Hierarchical classifiers

2.2 Activity Monitoring in XR Training Environments

XR technologies are increasingly used for training in industrial, medical, and educational domains due to their ability to simulate complex operational scenarios while capturing detailed user interaction data [15]. XR platforms inherently provide spatial tracking of user movements together with contextual information about the virtual scene, enabling monitoring approaches that directly relate human motion to task-relevant elements.

Several studies have explored XR-based training environments for performance assessment and procedural learning. Reviews of XR training systems highlight their potential to support data-driven evaluation of user behavior during

complex tasks [16]. Other works investigate XR-assisted maintenance systems designed to improve task guidance and usability in industrial contexts [33].

Despite these advances, most XR training research focuses primarily on instructional delivery, learning outcomes, and user experience evaluation rather than detailed monitoring of activity execution [34, 35]. In particular, relatively few works investigate how motion analysis and task-aware representations can be integrated to monitor procedural execution during XR training sessions.

The approach proposed in this work builds on these ideas by integrating motion-level monitoring with task-structured representations in order to analyze how trainees perform procedural tasks within an XR-based training environment.

3 Methodology

XR environments provide a unique sensing infrastructure for HAMA. Unlike conventional monitoring systems relying on external cameras or wearable sensors [19], XR devices natively provide synchronized spatial tracking of head and hand movements together with contextual information about the virtual scene, user interactions, and task progression [15]. This integration enables monitoring approaches that directly relate user motion to task-relevant objects and procedural states within the training environment.

Building on these capabilities and the paradigms introduced in Section 2, this work investigates the implementation of a multi-level HAMA strategy within an XR-based industrial training scenario. The proposed approach combines trajectory-level similarity metrics with task-phase monitoring to characterize activity execution during procedural training tasks. This section first describes the XR training scenario and then presents the monitoring approach.

3.1 The Demonstration Use Case

The proposed monitoring approach is investigated in a pilot study developed at TAP Air Portugal. The scenario addresses maintenance training for Aircraft Maintenance Technicians (AMTs) on a critical aircraft subsystem, the Wing Anti-Ice Valve (WAIV), using immersive XR environments designed to support complex procedural tasks. Traditional aircraft maintenance training relies on manuals, videos, and supervised practice sessions. While effective, these approaches provide limited opportunities for repeated practice under realistic conditions and offer little real-time guidance during task execution. XR technologies enable interactive training environments where maintenance procedures can be simulated using digital models of aircraft components, allowing technicians to rehearse operations safely and repeatedly.

The training environment is implemented as a Unity-based XR application running on Meta Quest devices in both Mixed Reality (MR) and Virtual Reality (VR) modalities. The application provides interactive 3D models of the WAIV assembly, as depicted in Fig. 1a, and guides operators through the procedural steps required for maintenance, as shown in Fig. 1b. Training materials and

Fig. 1: WAIV maintenance procedure within XR environments

workflows are authored through a dedicated Training Platform and delivered to XR devices through Hololight Stream⁴ infrastructure.

A central element of the system is the Human Digital Twin (HDT) of the AMT. The HDT component, implemented using the Clawdite platform⁵ [36], captures movements of expert technicians and uses them as reference models within the HAMA approach. During training sessions, the HDT enables three complementary capabilities: (i) *Shadowing*, where expert movements are recorded and replayed in the XR environment as a visual overlay to guide the trainee during the procedure (Fig. 1c and Fig. 1d); (ii) *Monitoring*, where trainee movements are continuously tracked in real-time during the procedure execution; (iii) *Performance Assessment*, where the tracked motion is compared with expert reference demonstrations to evaluate execution quality and detect deviations.

Motion data is captured directly through the XR headset (i.e., Meta Quest 3), which provides 53 tracked body points per sample: the head pose and 26 skeletal joints per hand - wrist, palm, and phalanges (metacarpal, proximal, intermediate, distal, and tip) of all five fingers - corresponding to the anatomical structure exposed by the Meta Quest hand tracking API. Each tracking point provides a 3D position and quaternion orientation (seven scalar values), yielding 371 raw values per sample at 10 Hz. Data are transmitted to the HDT platform together with contextual information such as the current procedural phase, user expertise level, and operator handedness, enabling monitoring that evaluates both motion accuracy and procedural progression.

⁴ <https://hololight.com/>

⁵ <https://clawdite.spslab.ch/>

3.2 Multi-level HAMA Approach

To analyze activity execution within this training scenario, a multi-level HAMA strategy was implemented combining trajectory analysis with task-level semantic information. The objective is to monitor how the maintenance procedure is executed rather than simply detecting individual actions.

Maintenance procedures are decomposed into operational phases defined by the XR application (e.g., WAIV approach, inspection, release). Within each phase, monitoring evaluates whether relevant milestones are achieved while simultaneously assessing movement quality with respect to expert reference executions. Motion sequences are compared using DTW, where similarity is computed through Euclidean distances between corresponding body-part positions weighted by body regions to reflect biomechanical relevance. Motion trajectories, orientations, and temporal dynamics are therefore analyzed to characterize how milestones are reached rather than enforcing exact trajectory replication.

Operationally, the monitoring pipeline processes tracking data through rolling temporal windows, enabling continuous assessment of activity execution at approximately one update per second. Deviation metrics are computed for each tracked body part and normalized using thresholds that depend on the current task phase and contextual operator information (e.g., expertise level). By combining motion analysis with phase-aware task monitoring, the approach improves robustness to execution speed variations and sensor noise while accommodating natural variability in user characteristics (e.g., height) and execution styles (e.g., left- or right-handed operation). At the same time, integrating procedural context increases the interpretability of monitoring results by linking detected deviations to specific task phases.

Based on this comparison, the system generates structured feedback describing detected issues and recommended corrective actions. Two complementary feedback mechanisms are currently implemented:

Rule-based, which provides deterministic low-latency feedback through pre-defined evaluation rules and guidance templates. Deviations are categorized by severity and prioritized according to biomechanical relevance and magnitude. When multiple deviations occur simultaneously, corrective suggestions are aggregated at body-region level to avoid cognitive overload.

LLM-based, which generates context-aware natural-language guidance. Prompts are constructed from quantitative monitoring outputs only: per-body-part deviation scores labeled by severity (critical: $> 2 \times$ threshold; warning: $>$ threshold; within range), the current task phase, operator skill level, and handedness. Providing structured numerical indicators rather than free-text interpretations limits the scope for hallucination to linguistic variation rather than diagnostic error, since the LLM cannot introduce sensor values or procedural facts absent from the input. The LLM must respond with a fixed JSON schema specifying a primary corrective action (max 80 characters), affected body region, severity level (1–10), and a status label; responses failing schema validation are discarded and rule-based output is used instead. Multiple providers are supported (OpenAI, Anthropic, and Google); the current default is Gemini-

Fig. 2: HAMA system supervision interface

2.5 Flash, achieving subsecond response times (typically ~ 0.5 s). Inference runs asynchronously, with automatic fallback to deterministic feedback if external services are unavailable, ensuring feedback delivery is uninterrupted. This design separates diagnostic reasoning, performed deterministically by the rule-based layer, from natural-language translation performed by the LLM, making system behavior auditable.

4 System

Within the current system, the monitoring pipeline is fully implemented, while feedback delivery remains external to the XR application. Corrective suggestions are therefore computed but not yet presented directly to the trainee, and formal evaluation involving real-time user interaction is deferred until full XR integration. Preliminary observations from actual XR session recordings confirm that the pipeline consistently identifies body regions exhibiting systematic deviations from expert trajectories, such as wrist positioning during valve approach and grip orientation during rotation phases, and correctly ranks them by severity across task phases. The asynchronous LLM component generates contextually coherent corrective suggestions (typically within ~ 0.5 s), complementing deterministic rule-based output and maintaining feedback availability.

Fig. 2 illustrates the monitoring interface used to visualize the system output. The dashboard aggregates motion deviation metrics and task-context information to provide an overview of trainee performance during the maintenance procedure. A color-coded scheme indicates performance status, where *green* denotes execution within the expert range, *yellow* highlights warning conditions, and *red* indicates critical deviations. The interface provides a global overview

of execution quality through aggregated deviation indicators, tracking status of monitored body parts, and temporal performance trends. Additional operational metrics support interpretation of monitoring results by reporting information such as tracking reliability, deviation thresholds, and short-term performance evolution. Corrective feedback is generated by the monitoring pipeline and visualized through the interface. Rule-based feedback produces prioritized suggestions aggregated by body region and severity level. When available, the LLM-based component generates contextual natural-language guidance derived from the same monitoring indicators, replacing the rule-based suggestion.

5 Conclusion

This paper investigated HAMA strategies for procedural tasks and introduced a work-in-progress multi-level HAMA system for XR-based training of aircraft maintenance technicians on a Wing Anti-Ice Valve. The work delivers three contributions. First, a conceptual taxonomy organizing HAMA paradigms from motion-centric to task-structured and multi-level monitoring, providing a framework for situating existing literature and guiding system design. Second, a real-time pipeline combining DTW-based motion comparison with phase-aware task monitoring on commodity XR hardware, without external cameras or specialized sensors. Third, a hybrid feedback architecture pairing deterministic rule-based evaluation with LLM-assisted natural-language generation, balancing feedback availability, auditability, and contextual appropriateness. Preliminary observations on session recordings confirm interpretable, phase-aware indicators, with LLM-generated feedback aligned with deterministic outputs.

Several limitations frame the next steps: monitoring accuracy and feedback quality have not yet been formally evaluated, the approach has been demonstrated in a single industrial use case, and the LLM component introduces a dependency on external services whose response consistency warrants systematic evaluation. Future work will pursue three directions: (i) in-XR integration of feedback delivery through visual overlays, audio, and haptic cues, to evaluate how modality affects learning outcomes; (ii) a formal user study with AMTs comparing training with and without real-time HAMA feedback, assessing procedural compliance, error rates, and time-to-competence; (iii) generalization to additional maintenance procedures and procedural domains such as surgical training and industrial assembly, to assess transferability of the multi-level paradigm.

More broadly, XR environments are well-suited as sensing platforms for multi-level activity monitoring, and as LLM capabilities and XR hardware mature, HAMA approaches are positioned to play a central role in the evolution from instructional platforms toward intelligent training systems.

Acknowledgements This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) and has been partially supported by the European Union’s research and innovation program under the project XR5.0 (Grant n.101135209).

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